

MICROELEKTRON NPS BLOCK
МИКРОЭЛЕКТРОН БЛОК НПС
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Azizov Asadulla Rakhimovich
Sindarov Feruz Sobir o'g'li
Tashkent State Transport University (Tashkent, Uzbekistan)

Азизов Асадулла Рахимович
Синдаров Феруз Собир ўғли
Ташкентский Государственный Транспортный Университет (Ташкент, Узбекистан)

Азизов Асадулла Рахимович
Синдаров Феруз Собир ўғли
Тошкент Давлат Транспорт Университети (Тошкент, Ўзбекистон)
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Annotation: This thesis proposes the development and practical application of an alternative version of the NPS block, belonging to the relay group, based on the technical requirements for railway automation and telemechanics equipment.

Key words: Class II relays. VU, PVU relays, current sensor, optocoupler, relay group block.

Аннотация: В этой тезисе предлагается разработка и практическое применение альтернативной версии блока НПС, относящегося к группе реле, на основе технических требований к оборудованию железнодорожной автоматики и телемеханики.

Ключевые слова: Реле II класса, Реле ВУ, ПВУ, датчик тока, оптопара, Блок группы набора.

Аннотация: Ушбу тезисда темирўл автоматикаси ва телемеханикаси аппаратурасига қўйилган техник талаблар асосида териш гурухига мансуб бўлган НПС блокиннинг муқобил вариантыни ишлаб чиқариш ва амалиётда қўллаш ҳақида таклиф келтирилади.

Калит сўзлар: II-синф релелар. ВУ, ПВУ релелар, Ток датчиги, оптожуфтлик, териш гурухи блоки.

Nowadays, developing process is going well in all sectors of our country, includes the Transport system. Uzbekistan Railways can be a striking example with its crucial role in our country's economy, with the rail sector being one of the most demanding industries. Given the significant share of rail transport in both international and domestic high-volume traffic, reducing downtime during all technological operations at stations is vital for the development of the industry and our economy. To achieve this, new energy-efficient, highly reliable, and high-speed microprocessor systems are being implemented in centralized railway transport systems. Currently, most railways in the country rely on electromagnetic and electromechanical relays in signaling centralization and blocking systems. These relays are known for their long service life and robust schematic design. Despite their high cost and the fact that they are imported, electromagnetic relays are still widely used. This article discusses

the development of a control microprocessor unit, the NPS, which manages the sequential insertion of switches in railway automation and telemechanics systems. It also covers its application in technological processes. The development of these units involves the use of electromagnetic relays as components and the replacement of relay contacts with small, energy-saving optocouplers. Before testing the NPS microprocessor block, each working circuit within the block can be individually checked, and the block's operation can be controlled by artificially applying voltage to the relays in the circuit. The device presented can be included in a set of microprocessor blocks to test all types of blocks. Special attention is given to the universality of the device during its creation, making it easy to maintain due to its small size and light weight. The device is simple and user-friendly. For blocks built using electromagnetic relays, it is necessary to send them to a control point to detect any defects, which is a result of the limited number of test benches for these types of blocks and their size and weight. With the increasing production of microprocessor devices, there are new requirements for the type and quality of service for these blocks.

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4. **Azizov Asadulla Rakhimovich** Tashkent state transport university. Candidate of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor, Department of Automation and Telemechanics in Railway Transport. E-mail: azizov.asadulla@mail.ru
5. **Sindarov Feruz Sobir o'g'li** Tashkent state transport university. Graduate student of Department of Automation and Telemechanics in Railway Transport. E-mail: feruzsindarov707@gmail.com